

РАЗВИТИЕ РЕЧИ УЧАЩИХСЯ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ОРФОГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ТЕМ**Худаёрова Гулнора Нуриддиновна**

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Аннотация. *Выполнение экзаменационной работы по русскому языку, да и по другим предметам, требует от выпускника школы следующих умений: анализировать, классифицировать языковые факты с целью обеспечения различных видов речевой деятельности; оценивать языковые явления с точки зрения нормативности; анализировать языковые единицы с точки зрения правильности, точности и уместности их употребления; использовать основные приёмы переработки текста, оценивать письменные высказывания с точки зрения языкового оформления, эффективности достижения поставленных коммуникативных задач; проводить лингвистический анализ текстов различных функциональных стилей и разновидностей языка; создавать собственное речевое высказывание в соответствии с поставленными задачами; осуществлять речевой самоконтроль.*

Ключевые слова: *оформления, владение, результат, становления.*

THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' SPEECH IN THE STUDY OF SPELLING TOPICS

Abstract. *Performing examination work in the Russian language, and in other subjects, requires the following skills from a school graduate: analyze, classify linguistic facts in order to ensure various types of speech activity; evaluate linguistic phenomena from the point of view of normativity; analyze language units in terms of correctness, accuracy and appropriateness of their use; use the basic methods of text processing, evaluate written statements in terms of language design, the effectiveness of achieving the set communicative tasks; conduct linguistic analysis of texts of various functional styles and varieties of language; create your own speech statement in accordance with the tasks; exercise self-control.*

Keywords: *design, possession, result, formation.*

INTRODUCTION

In this regard, the possession of spelling literate writing today is considered as an indicator of the speech development of schoolchildren, therefore, work on the development of students' speech in the process of studying spelling topics is one of the leading goals of the educational process. "Since success in mastering spelling depends on the general speech development of students, it is necessary at each lesson to combine grammar tasks with elements of speech activity"¹. Thus, the development of spelling literacy is possible only as a result of a purposeful, coordinated development of all types of speech activity (reading, listening, speaking and writing). From the course of grammar and spelling orientation "Russian language" from the beginning of the 90s. 20th century turned into a course with a pronounced speech orientation. Purely spelling priorities "disappear", become different, namely, aimed at the formation of a coordinated unity of spelling and speech skills necessary for the development of literate writing in the practice of speech communication.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Meanwhile, one often hears: spelling rules (namely, they form the basis of the school spelling course) are so difficult for children that when studying spelling topics, there is no time

left for work on the development of speech. This profound misconception is based on a misunderstanding of the correlation between the work on mastering the linguistic essence of spelling rules (phonetic, lexical, grammatical, semantic) and on the development of students' speech. Only the connection of these directions, as experience shows, makes it possible to master the linguistic content essence of spelling rules and rely on it in the course of writing, thereby ensuring the unity of language and thinking, the unity of theory and practice, knowledge and skills.

RESULTS

Teaching spelling in a modern school is a systematic work on:

- a) the assimilation of spelling concepts, designed to ensure the solid formation of literate writing skills;
- b) the assimilation of spelling norms on the basis of identifying and systematizing the linguistic content that constitutes the basic essence of each spelling rule;
- c) expanding the vocabulary of students;
- d) enrichment of the grammatical structure of speech;
- e) improvement of all types of speech activity (reading, listening, speaking and writing) in their unity and interconnection.

The assimilation of spelling and speech skills and abilities is achieved by a variety of exercises, gradually becoming more complex from stage to stage and consistently based on the types of speech activity and its types - receptive, reproductive, productive, which reflects the gradation of spelling and speech skills and abilities: from working with a sample (receptive activities) - to independent work on the analysis and synthesis of spellings in a finished speech model (text) (reproductive activity) and, finally, to creative work (productive activity). This arrangement of the material provides a conscious study, consolidation and repetition of the content (linguistic) essence of the spelling rules necessary for the formation of literate writing, and contributes to the intensive speech development of students. Spelling is the skill of writing. In its development, constant exercises are important, which should not only form the skill, but also activate and develop the thought and speech of students.

In the process of teaching the Russian language, students must master spelling literacy and be able to consistently, accurately and clearly, as well as grammatically correctly express their thoughts.

Therefore, one of the most important tasks of studying the Russian language at school remains the formation of strong spelling skills among schoolchildren, since spelling-literate writing is an essential element of the general language culture and every educated person needs to master it, which is determined by the function of the language as a means of communicating people with each other in various fields of activity.

Written speech, one of the essential aspects of which is spelling, is no less significant in the process of communication than oral speech. In writing, in order to understand the meaning of what is written, it is necessary to observe not only spelling, but also grammatical, punctuation and stylistic norms.

The low level of schoolchildren's written language culture is explained primarily by the fact that until now, in the practice of teaching the Russian language, such a situation has persisted when spelling is taught in isolation from the development of speech and absorbs the

maximum time allotted by the curriculum for learning the Russian language, and the processes of forming spelling and speech skills develop in parallel, little in contact with each other.

Nevertheless, the spelling technique at the present stage has been enriched with fundamentally important provisions, one of which is the relationship between the formation of spelling skills and work on the development of speech.

Spelling skills are formed by memorizing the rules, memorizing the spelling of words, but exercises play a decisive role. The exercise "acts as a carrier of the content of training and a means of its assimilation, as a way of organizing and managing educational and cognitive activities"².

Knowledge of the rules alone is not enough for literate writing, since their visual development is necessary, and in the course of the exercise, the generalizations learned by students in the form of rules are transferred to similar, typical cases, which contributes to the formation and consolidation of spelling skills and abilities.

DISCUSSION

Based on the existing scientific terminology on the theory of methodology, we understand teaching methods as "ways of interaction between a teacher and students, under the leadership of a teacher, aimed at achieving learning goals" and refer exercises to teaching methods. So, academician A.V. Tekuchev writes: "One of the important methods of teaching the Russian language is a system of methodically thought-out, diverse in nature ... exercises"³. The separation of spelling from the tasks of developing speech in the learning process is one of the main reasons for the lag of students in the Russian language.

The modern method of teaching the Russian language has valuable experience in scientific research that highlights the issues of teaching spelling and the development of speech. However, the presence of independent methods for spelling and speech development, as it were, reinforces the gap in the formation of spelling and speech skills that has become a tradition and the two-dimensional nature of the work of a Russian language teacher.

The amount of study time allocated to the study of the Russian language does not allow the teacher to work in two ways and forces him to look for new, more effective ways to improve the skills of literate written speech. It seems to us appropriate to put the teaching of spelling in an organic connection with the development of speech.

Usually, in the theory and practice of teaching the Russian language, creative and free dictations are considered as a means of developing students' speech, and few methodologists mention the restored dictation in their works. For this reason, the role of non-specialized teaching methods in the process of working on spelling (as mentioned above) has not been specifically studied, although this was convincingly mentioned in the works of many well-known scientists (K.B. Barkhin, M.V. Ushakov, N.S. Rozhdestvensky, M.T. Baranov, T.A. Ladyzhenskaya, and others).

Researches of scientists have shown that to automate skills, exercises are needed in which the learned would be applied in more difficult conditions, the knowledge gained would be included in creative activity. Such conditions are created when performing creative and combined exercises, as well as using active and interactive teaching methods, as they further activate the mental activity of students and provide a better understanding and memorization of the material being studied.

Creative exercises, during which students go through “the stage of “combining” two tasks: to express their thoughts in writing and at the same time observe spelling norms”⁴; these practical methods, unfortunately, are relegated to the background and exist only as potentially possible: teachers either do not use them in Russian language lessons, or use them only as exercises for the development of coherent speech. However, with this approach to learning (even despite great efforts), it is impossible to achieve high rates in the assimilation of spelling by students, since a paradoxical situation arises: students correctly reproduce the spelling rule, select a large number of examples for one spelling, distinguish one spelling from another, group words according to the given spellings, acting according to the appropriate algorithm, but as soon as the students get into the conditions of independent writing, all this knowledge remains unclaimed. This is precisely due to the one-sided choice of exercises, the rare use of some works, which are one of the real means of strengthening the relationship between the formation of spelling skills and the work on speech development.

Students are often helpless when they find themselves in the conditions of independent writing, since when developing spelling skills, teachers do not use exercises that combine spelling and speech development.

CONCLUSIONS

The study of the long history of scientific research and pedagogical experience (the works of K.D. Ushinsky, N.S. Rozhdestvensky, M.V. Ushakov) convinces us that only those teachers achieve a strong and conscious assimilation of spelling, which put the teaching of spelling in close connection with the development of students' speech.

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